

Effect of planting time on SR incidence at Kaul, India.

Variety	Infected tillers (%)				Reduction in disease (%) over 18 Jul planting	
	18 Jul	3 Aug	18 Aug	Mean	3 Aug planting	8 Aug planting
Jaya	59	35	3	32	40	95
Jhona 349	19	80	25	61	-2	68
Pusa 33	66	62	5	44	6	92
Basmati 310	25	15	1	14	42	95
HAU 118-110	11	5	3	6	53	76
HAUK 2313-39	24	19	3	15	19	86
Mean	44	36	7			

CD at 5%

For comparison of means of 2 planting dates
For comparison of means of 2 varieties
For interaction (planting date × variety)

4.52
2.14
4.14

varieties except Jhona 349 was significantly less in the 3 Aug planting. This was attributed to lower temperatures (23°C) and relative humidity (69%) during susceptible stages (see table). *ℒ*

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Pest Control and Management INSECTS

Influence of plant density on oviposition by whorl maggot (RWM)

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We studied the influence of spacing of transplanted and wet seeded IR36 on the number of RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino eggs laid per plant and the degree of RWM damage.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with planting methods as main plots and plant and seed density as subplots. In transplanted plots, hill spacings were 10 × 10, 20 × 20, and 40 × 40 cm. In wet seeded plots, seed rates were 160, 120, and 80 kg/ha. Three seedlings per hill were transplanted 15 d after sowing. Pregerminated seeds were sown in wet seeded plots on the same day. Plots were flooded 3 d after sowing

RWM damage and egg density as affected by plant density in transplanted and wet seeded IR36.^a IRRI, 1983 DS.

Plant density	Eggs (no.) at indicated days after transplanting or sowing						Damaged leaves (%) 23 DT/DS
	Per m ²			Per plant			
	8	18	28	8	18	28	
<i>Transplanted</i>							
Spacing							
10 × 10 cm	124 c	481 c	179 b	1.2 a	4.9 a	1.8 a	54 a
20 × 20 cm	319 b	192 b	135 b	12.8 b	7.7 b	5.4 a	65 ab
40 × 40 cm	183 a	139 a	70 a	29.3 c	22.1 c	112 b	15 b
<i>Wet seeded</i>							
Seed rate (kg/ha)							
160 kg/ha	189 c	223 b	110 b	0.39 a	0.41 a	0.23 a	21 a
120 kg/ha	132 b	204 b	81 b	0.66 b	1.02 a	0.44 a	37 a
80 kg/ha	61 a	119 a	76 a	1.36 c	2.38 b	1.52 b	52 b

^a Av of 4 replications. In a column under each planting method, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

and transplanting. Number of eggs was counted in a 1-m quadrat and expressed on a per area and per plant basis.

For both planting methods, eggs were most abundant by area on the more densely spaced plants (see table). *ℒ*

Effect of nitrogen and carbofuran on gall midge (GM) and white stem borer (SB) infestation in Nigeria

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In 1984 wet season we studied the effect of N fertilizer and granular carbofuran application on GM *Orseolia oryzivora*

Harris and Gagne and white SB *Maliarpha separatella* Ragonot infestation on rice plants at Badeggi, Nigeria. The site was on the irrigated lowland research farm of NCRI.

The field trial was in a split-plot randomized block design with three replications on an acid Oxisol (Agaie soil series). Three-week-old FARO 15 seedlings were planted in 15-m² plots at 20 × 2 km spacing. N as ammonium

sulfate was applied at 0, 50, 100, or 150 kg/ha as 50% basal and 25% each at active tillering and panicle initiation. Basal P and K were 40 kg/ha. Carbofuran granules (1.0 kg ai/ha) were applied at 1, 30, and 60 d after transplanting (DT); 1 and 30 DT; 30 and 60 DT. GM damage was measured at 70 DT as the number of onion shoots to total tillers in 50 hills/plot. SB damage was measured by dissecting